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TELECONFERENCE AS A MEANS OF INTERACTIVE TRAINING OF IN-SERVICE TEACHERS

Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel¹ and Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari²

Abstract

Teaching is a dynamic activity. Teacher needs to be updated about the latest developments in the field of education. Most of the teachers, despite of their long years of teaching experience remain unaware of latest developments and lack updated information about processes and products of education. They lack their continuous training which is created after regular pre-service training. If they are trained in a regular pre-service programme then how long lasting is the one-year or two-year training to cope up with life long challenges in teaching is a major question. Hence, there appears a need of in-service training on new issues. All teachers can not be trained face to face in cascade mode in all the emerging areas. Therefore, Information Communication Technology (ICT) appears as a technique of training for in-service training. Teleconference as an aspect of ICT has a major role in in-service training of teachers. This article gives an introduction, background, arrangement of teleconference. The authors have also discussed problem faced during the conduct of teleconference, listed out the stakeholders, suggestive themes, merits and demerits of teleconference. It is mentioned the teleconference is a best way to have interactive produce for in-service training.

INTRODUCTION

India is a large country with huge population. The percentage of school going population is quite large. This is why the central and state government are extending schooling facilities for children from 6-14 and beyond. In an effort to this the schemes like DPEP, SSA and present project of RMSA have opened new schools and recruited new teachers. But, the number of actual trained teachers to take up the challenge of new system of education is less. Moreover, teaching faculty consists of teachers who have service of large number of years. This creates a need for up gradation of their knowledge of concept, theories of teaching etc. as they have passed their pre-service training long ago. The growing numbers of content areas of training, increased requirement of training teachers, and continuous research leading to new areas of researches have made us to think of innovative ways of training in-service teachers. It is worthwhile to note here that traditional, face-to-face, cluster level in-service trainings are insufficient and inadequate. Hence, new technologies are emerging which can help large groups simultaneously, thereby saving time, effort, finance and energy. This has increased use of ICT like teleconferencing in education.

Teleconferencing

The academic training programme in the form of training of distant learner from a centrally located teaching centre is called teleconferencing. Here the learning ends are geographically widespread, but the learners are assembled in real time at different learning ends and interact with faculty at training end. This is an organised, well planned, training programme. In this teaching and learning ends are connected through satellite transmission and telephone connections.

“Teleconferencing refers to interactive electronic communication among teachers-learners and learners-learners located at more than two places. The concepts of active process and active dialogue come to the fore in teleconferencing. Thus, interactivity has a central role in learning at distance”. Dash (2010, P. 9)

Teleconferencing helps in dissemination of information right from the horse mouth or experts of the persons working in the field. Hence, the doubts of learners can be clarified on the spot. The transmission loss which occurs during cascade mode is removed or reduced. General teleconferencing can be telecast through public channels or websites can cover practically large number of learners. Practically the lessons are transmitted to all intended learner geographically widespread and to give an analogy this mode act like a public address system (PAS) used in limited geographical area (of course no feedback mechanism is available PAS).

¹ Associate Professor in Education, DDE, MANUU, Hyderabad

² Research Assistant, CSSEIP, MANUU, Gachibowli, Hyderabad

Teleconferencing helps in integration of media inputs. The teleconferencing makes use of media like audio, video, computer, print, phone, fax and works through satellite services.

The word 'tele' means distance. The word 'conference' means consultations, discussions. Through teleconferencing two or more locations situated at a distance are connected so that they can hear or both see and hear each other. It allows the distant sites to interact with each other and with the teaching end through phone, fax, and e-mail. The interactions occur in real time. This means that the learners/participants and the resource persons are present at the same time in different locations and are able to communicate with each other. In some situations, questions can be faxed/e-mailed early for response by the resource persons. (CEMCA 2004, P. 11)

Types of Teleconferencing

The majority of the institutes have adopted two-way audio and one-way video system of teleconferencing. The Andhra Pradesh Government has extensively used two-way audio and two-way video teleconferencing for administrative purposes in the beginning of this millennium. Some departments made use of phone conferencing like in case of irrigation department of Karnataka in 2002. The Government of Karnataka under its DEP-DPEP (Distance Education Programme – District Primary Education Programme) extensively used radio phone-in conference from different radio stations. Some of the departments have ventured in use of computer conferencing for educational programmes.

Background of Teleconferencing

The first teleconference was conducted on AIDS, which was broadcast from Quito. This was broadcast for 300 receiving sites. The NCERT in India was pioneer in use of teleconferencing. The initial attempts were made to train teachers in Mathematics and English from North-Eastern India in 1996-97. The successful attempts helped in launch of national level project to support DPEP. The project was christened DEP-DPEP and IGNOU was given the responsibility of its implementation from 1998 till 2003. During this project Distance Education Co-ordinators were appointed in all DPEP states and Distance Education activities were successfully conducted. The common feature of this period was conduct of teleconferencing in all DPEP districts of DPEP state, where Direct Reception System (DRS) were installed in DIETs. The successful conduct of these events lead to extension of DEP activities in Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, where the use of teleconferencing was even extended to blocks and in some states to cluster levels.

Arrangements of Teleconferencing

A basic model of two-way audio and one-way video teleconference is being depicted in a graphical way as under,

The teaching end transmits signals both audio and via satellite to the learning end via satellite. The learning end contacts teaching end through telephone line.

The planning of teleconferencing is done both the ways: from the headquarter, who identifies issue what can go as input for training or needs can also be raised by grass root functionaries demanding areas of training. This is followed by identification of resource persons, experts, stakeholders, learning centres, financial requirement, transmission end, scheduling of events etc. The important arrangements made are discussed below,

Development of Self Learning Material (SLM)

This is based on the theme of teleconference and gives thematic interpretation of concepts of training. The SLM of teleconference is a small book containing of about 10-15 pages, which are written in interactive format. Each of the SLM emphasises 3-4 sections, which are discussed in the training by the teaching end. The learners or trainees are also suggested to carry out various activities in groups, when the lesson is not transmitted from studio. The consolidated report is prepared by each centre as suggested in the SLM. The writing of SLM is simple, interactive and has provisions for recording the activities. The SLM is also a document of particular

conference and hence, should also contain information like theme of conference, organisers, date, time and schedule and resource persons involved.

Schedule of activities

The activities conducted during the conference are called scheduled activities. These involve, teaching, learning, interaction, group work and mainly classified into online and offline activities. A sample / suggestive schedule are given below.

Time	On-Air / Off-Air	Activity
Theme: School Readiness		
09.00 – 10.00	Off-Air	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reporting of previous day’s work – Briefing about day’s topics – Study of module: School Readiness
Studio end activities		
10.00 – 10.30		
10.00 – 11.15	On-Air	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Introduction to the topic School Readiness and the panellists – Presentation-cum-Demonstration on School Readiness
10.30 – 11.15– Participants interact with the panellists		
– Summing up and instructions for group activity		
11.15 – 11.30	Off-Air	Tea Break
11.30 – 12.10	Off-Air	Group activities and discussion among the participants on the guidelines provided
Participants interact with the panellists		
12.10 – 13.00	On-Air	Summary key points
Brief next session		
13.00 – 14.00	Off-Air	Lunch Break
TOPIC : MULTIGRADE TEACHING		
14.00 – 14.20	Off-Air	Study of the module : Multi-grade teaching
Introduction to the topic Multi-grade teaching and the panellists		
14.20 – 14.50	On-Air	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Discussion on problems of school management – Time schedule and teaching learning strategies in

		multi-grade classes illustrated with video excerpts and situational analysis.
		Participants interact with the panellist
14.50 – 15.50	On-Air	– Summing up – Instructions for group activities
15.50 – 16.00	Off-Air	Tea Break
16.00 – 16.35	Off-Air	Group activities/discussion among participants on the guidelines provided
16.35 – 17.20	On-Air	– Participants interact with the panellists – Summing up

Modified form of Source: Phalachandra B. (1997) Report on Primary Teachers' Training through Interactive Video Technology, NCERT, New Delhi, India.

The online activities are those activities of teleconference, which make use of online transmission. The transmission process is used for providing the training and interaction. The training sessions involve presentation of facts, theoretical concepts, demonstration, examples by use of sound, picture, animation or movie picture. During these sessions one expert or group of experts present their ideas. The computers can help in presenting power point presentations and tele-top can be made use while projecting handwritten materials. The online sessions are used to clarify doubts and queries of learner. The learners put forth their ideas through phone, fax, email, sms or through web-cameras based on the available facilities. The experts from teaching end or studio can give adequate feedback to the learners. Majority of the responses are given online for the benefit of learners, however, if so desire the organisers can record all the observations and publish it for the benefit of learners.

Teaching End

The studio, which transmits the signals of the programme, is the teaching end. This end houses resource persons, media experts, officials, who are involved in the arrangements of dissemination of information. The experts device, decide their talk, time; interact individually or collectively in panel during presentation and interact with learning ends. The media expert help in positioning camera, mixing of images, audio, video or any other media giving vivid impact and providing telephone, fax facility to enhance interactivity.

Learning End

The learning end is a place of learning and receives transmission from studio via satellite. This is equipped with telephone, television, fax, Direct Reception System (DRS) and power backup for reception of signals. The stakeholders at receiving end involve facilitators and learners. They are supplied with instruction and SLM, which also includes programme schedule of particular teleconference. The learners follow the instruction given. The on air session are used to follow the lectures, debates and off air sessions are used for conduct of group activities and general breaks for tea / coffee or lunch.

Problems faced during conduct of Teleconference

Organisation of teleconference is a massive task, which involves at least 30 persons in each centre and about 20 such centres are part of a teleconference programme. In addition to this there are large number of resource persons, technical staff, facilitators and support staff involved. Thus, assembling of hundreds of people desirous of learning one theme is quite a gigantic task. These programmes are planned in a short duration. In such a situation printing and supply of SLM becomes difficult for offices / institutes organising the programme. The officials who facilitate such programme change their academic and administrative roles, hence, training of these personnel have direct impact on learning faculty. Competent facilitators ensure better learning, where as in competent facilitators make the effort just a gathering like 'Mela' or 'fair'. The experts in the teaching are to be

familiar of content and media requirements. The role of facilitators is to control the proceedings are also very important. Failure of facilitators carries the entire conference in the wrong direction.

Stakeholders

The stakeholders of teleconference are all those, who are involved in education process. This means teachers, cluster resource persons, block resource persons, DIET faculty, CTE faculty, education officers, school development and monitoring committee members, parents etc. are the stakeholders. They are provided training as and when it is required and this is based on the theme. As far as present article is concerned the in-service teachers teaching in different subject areas, mediums of instructions, level of teaching and different experience are stakeholders.

Merits and Demerits of Teleconference

The teleconference has merits and demerits. Some important aspects are discussed below.

Merits

- The participants undergo similar experience pertaining to every theme or module of learning.
- The process helps in reducing transmission loss, which occurs in cascade mode of training.
- The cascade mode, which involves face to face training requires large amount of expenditure, more time and efforts.
- The authorities of education department, who are part of training understand ground realities and know the basic problems.
- Enhance democratic values of sharing and respect ideas. Officers cannot neglect ideas put forth by learners during on air transmission.

Demerits

- Finding good facilities both at teaching and learning end is difficult.
- This is more power dependent and technology oriented process.
- Supply of printed SLM becomes difficulty due to paucity of time and hence effect of printed material is absent.
- All the centres cannot present their queries through phone due to lack of connectivity.

Academic Issues or themes for Teleconferencing

There are innumerable areas, which can be taken up for training of stake holders. These include new or upcoming areas in school education. Some of the areas on which teleconferencing can be conducted and suggestive participants who can be called for training are listed below

Sl. No.	Theme / Issues	Participants at learning end
1.	Right to education	Community, officials, teachers, parents
2.	Introduction of new syllabus	Teachers
3.	Introduction of English at Primary Level	Primary teachers teaching English
4.	Role of School Development and Monitoring Committees (SDMC) in school building	SDMC members
5.	Development of activity based evaluation	Primary teachers

6.	Conduct of district level Science exhibition and Science fair	High school science teachers
7.	Multi-grade teaching	Primary teachers
8.	Monitoring of midday meals scheme implementation	Educational administrators
9.	Conducting review of project (like SSA)	Educational administrators

In addition to some areas of training of teachers, training of few other stakeholders is also listed above for clarity of the requirements of training.

Patel (2003) has listed various teleconferences taken up under, DEP-DPEP in Karnataka. These include,

- a. Interactive satellite based communication to the teachers
- b. Orientation for Chinnara Angala Field functionaries
- c. Orientation regarding children census 2002,
- d. Chinnara Angala & SDMC training
- e. Training of BRPs, CRPs regarding Keli-Kali programme
- f. Training of DRPs regarding 7th All India School Survey
- g. Training of DRPs regarding Urdu Keli-Kali
- h. Teleconference for parents of IED children
- i. Radio phone-in conference

During these teleconference a large amount positive feedback was also found by the author and there by the programme was extended in the form of EDUSAT project for Primary schools in Karnataka.

CONCLUSION

The teleconference is an immediate solution for meeting needs of larger number of population in education. If it is used in a proper way this strength of Information Communication Technology can have a very good impact on education system. Large number of innovations are also appearing in the form of computer conferencing and this has to be utilised in school education and training of personnel. Teleconferencing is the best form of in-service teacher training.

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